

treatments and weed control methods, including a weed-free and weedy check, were main plot treatments.

Seedlings were transplanted in lines at 20- × 20- cm spacing in a field fertilized with 5 t farmyard manure/ha. Hand and rotary weeding were performed once at 35 d after transplanting (DT), or twice at 21 and 40 DT. Butachlor granules were broadcast 2 DT at 2 kg ai/ha with or without one hand or rotary weeding at 35 DT. Weeding costs were estimated on the basis of current labor charges, cost of herbicide, and time taken to apply it.

A minimum 10 m² from the center of each plot was harvested to determine grain yield. Weed control methods were compared to local farmer practice (one hand weeding) by calculating return above variable cost (RAVC) and marginal benefit-to-cost ratio (MBCR).

Principal weed species were *Cyperus rotundus* and *Fimbristylis miliacea*. Other species found were *Cyperus* spp., *Cynodon dactylon*, *Echinochloa* spp. and *Paspalum distichum*. All weed control treatments gave a significantly higher yield than the weedy check (see table). Response of the varieties to the treatments was broadly similar. The highest yields, comparable to that of the weed-free check, came from the butachlor treatments and were not significantly different from yields with one or two hand or rotary weeding. There was no yield advantage in supplementing butachlor with hand or rotary weeding. A single rotary weeding 35 DT appeared to be more effective than a single hand weeding, and was statistically comparable to 2 rotary weeding.

Compared with farmer practice (one hand weeding), rotary weeding treatments had substantial RAVC, reflecting both reduced costs and increased benefits. But unlike the alternative weed control treatments, which can be applied in randomly planted rice (the common practice in Wangdiphodrang), rotary weeding requires line planting. That may entail increased costs if more planting time is needed.

Of the remaining treatments, a second hand weeding gave some economic advantage over farmer practice, but a single application of butachlor was outstanding economically.

Both butachlor and rotary weeding appear to be promising labor-saving weed control methods in rice under Bhutanese conditions. □

Weeds disseminated with rice seedlings

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In Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, we observed that weed seedlings and weed seeds were disseminated with rice seedlings during transplanting. An average of 51 weed seedlings were counted in each of 450 rice seedling bundles, which contained an average 684 rice seedlings. Farmers did not separate out the weed seedlings before transplanting.

Fourteen species belonging to five families were transplanted with the rice seedlings: the most common were

Echinochloa glabrescens and *Paspalum distichum* (see table). These weeds are highly competitive with rice and difficult to control.

An average 427 weed seeds were found attached to the roots of rice seedlings in each of 300 bundles examined. Twenty weed species, predominantly *Cyperus difformis*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Rotala catholica*, and *Lindernia antipoda*, which were disseminated in this manner, added to the weed seed reserves in the soil. Depending on dormancy and viability, they will be a source of infestation, not only in the crop in which they were disseminated but also in future crops. □

Weeds disseminated with rice seedlings in farmers fields, Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines.

Weed species	Family	Seedlings (no.)	Seeds (no.)
<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.	Lythraceae	—	10.5
<i>Ammannia octandra</i> L. f.	Lythraceae	—	16.2
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	Cyperaceae	5.7	104.0
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	Cyperaceae	0.1	3.3
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	1.1	1.8
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Poaceae	1.2	—
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	Poaceae	3.1	2.8
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook. f.	Poaceae	10.9	9.3
<i>Echinochloa oryzoides</i> (Ard.) Fritsch.	Poaceae	5.0	—
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	0.1	3.3
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	Cyperaceae	4.4	86.5
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	Poaceae	0.9	—
<i>Lindernia antipoda</i> (L.) Alston	Scrophulariaceae	0.1	65.7
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i> (Jacq.) Raven	Onagraceae	—	2.8
<i>Ludwigia perennis</i> L.	Onagraceae	—	6.7
<i>Melochia concatenata</i> L.	Sterculiaceae	—	0.2
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl	Pontederiaceae	0.3	25.2
<i>Paspalum distichum</i> L.	Poaceae	13.6	0.8
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	Poaceae	—	0.3
<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Schum. & Thonn.	Euphorbiaceae	—	0.3
<i>Rotala catholica</i> (Cham. & Schlecht.) B. van Leeuwen	Lythraceae	—	67.5
<i>Scirpus supinus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	4.8	18.7
<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i> L.	Aizoaceae	—	1.5

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